

Independence and Time Reversal in Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 4, 2019

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) relationship for momentum $P(p)$, proportional to $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$, is often derived from maximization of entropy or from the Boltzmann transport equation. In this note, we suggest the MB, as well as steady fluid flow and traditional quantum mechanical temperature statistics seem to follow from a reaction relationship of the form $P(p_1)\text{Reaction}(p_1 \text{ to } p_2) = P(p_2)\text{Reaction}(p_2 \text{ to } p_1)$ which upon taking the natural logarithm has the appearance of a reaction conservation equation $\ln(P(p_1)) - \ln(P(p_2)) = \text{Function}$. If there is a mechanical conservation law present in the system, such as conservation of energy (including kinetic energy), one may try to compare the two conservation laws and identify $\ln(P(p_1))$ with $p^2/2m$ or an analogous energy term to obtain an MB type distribution. In the case of the ground state quantum oscillator $P(p) = C \exp(-p^2/E)$, so we argue a similar “reaction” conservation law applies, related to “independence” and “time reversal balance”. Thus, the ground state quantum oscillator yields the same statistics at the $P(x)$, $P(p)$ level as classical statistical mechanics. This begs the question: Why does such a relationship not hold for other oscillator states or for other potentials? We argue in this note, that in bound state quantum mechanics there are two velocities, $v_{rms}(x) = v(x)$ (from the square root of the classical velocity from an energy conservation equation) and $u = (1/W) d/dx W$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. For the case of the ground state oscillator: $C_1 v(x) \cdot v(x) + C_2 u(x) \cdot u(x) = E$, so both $v(x)$ and $u(x)$ follow Newton’s law and so it is as if there is one velocity. This, we argue, seems to imply that one has independence of p ’s (momenta) scattering with $V(x)$ and time reversal balance. For all other cases of bound state quantum mechanics, it seems that $v(x)$ and $u(x)$, both “average” velocities in the system, follow different kinematics implying that one cannot write equations of the following form: $P(p_1)\text{Reaction}(p_1 \text{ to } p_2) = P(p_2)\text{Reaction}(p_2 \text{ to } p_1)$. Thus, even though mechanical conservation laws may exist, one cannot compare them with the log of probability equations to obtain a Maxwell-Boltzmann type distribution.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution with no Fluid Flow

For the case of no fluid flow, one may go to any point in a gas (even with a potential $V(x)$) and consider two particle scattering. Thus:

$p_1 + p_2 \rightarrow p_3 + p_4$ Here p_i is a momentum vector and there is conservation of momentum as well as of kinetic energy, as elastic scattering is assumed. We argue, from “and” probability that:

$$P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_3)P(p_4) \quad ((1))$$

This is a strong statement, but seems to imply each type of scattering reaction is independent, so one wants a time reversal balance at this level. ((1)) ensures $P(p)$ does not change in time,

and because it is enforced at the level of a specific reaction, one need not to worry about other types of reactions. They too enforce a time reversal balance. Taking the natural logarithm of ((1)) leads to a conservation type equation:

$$\ln(P(p1)) + \ln(P(p2)) = \ln(P(p3)) + \ln(P(p4)) \quad ((2))$$

Now the only mechanical conservation law in the system (not dependent on the sign of p) seems to be conservation of kinetic energy:

$$p1^2/2m + p2^2/2m = p3^2/2m + p4^2/2m \quad ((3))$$

Thus, one may try to match ((2)) and ((3)) to argue that:

$\ln(P(p1)) = C p1^2/2m$ which leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann relationship.

In the case of a potential $V(x)$: $p1^2/2m + V(x1) = p2^2/2m + V(x2)$ suggesting that the distribution should be of the form:

$$\exp(-p^2/2m + V(x)) \quad ((4))$$

It should be noted that independence of scattering reactions and time reversal appear to be key in this argument.

Steady Flow Statistical Mechanics

It is also possible to have steady flow in a system with $u(x)$ the flow velocity vector which has no time dependence. In (1), a distribution of $f(p, x) = C \exp(- (p-u(x))^2)$ ((5)) is assumed with $u(x) = \text{Ave}(v f(p,x))$. Flow equations are developed from the Boltzmann transport equation and one ultimately obtains:

$$\text{density}(x) = C1 \exp[-(.5m u(x)^2 + V(x)/T)] \quad ((6))$$

If $u(x)=0$ one obtains the static spatial dependence of ((4)). It should be noted that ((5)) is of the form of a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution with collective velocity $u(x)$ removed. As a result, consider two particle scattering with $u(x)$ removed. Then conservation of momentum suggests:

$$p1-u(x) + p2-u(x) = p3 - u(x) + p4-u(x) \quad ((7)) \text{ Here all terms are vectors.}$$

And

$$(p1-u)^2/2m + (p2-u)^2/2m = (p3-u)^2/2m + (p4-u)^2/2m \text{ implies:}$$

$p_1^2/2m + p_2^2/2m = p_3^2/2m + p_4^2/2m$ ((8)) because $\mathbf{u} \cdot (\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2) = \mathbf{u} \cdot (\mathbf{p}_3 + \mathbf{p}_4)$ by momentum conservation. Thus, one has conservation of relative kinetic energy at a point x . This may suggest:

$$P(p_1 - u)P(p_2 - u) = P(p_3 - u)P(p_4 - u) \quad ((9))$$

This is an “and” probability condition applied to momenta with $u(x)$ removed. Here $m=1$. Taking the natural logarithm of ((9)) and comparing with ((8)) leads to $\exp[-(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{u})/T]$. Thus, time reversal and independence seem to be involved again.

Quantum Mechanical Gas

In a traditional quantum mechanical gas at temperature T , one considers single particle levels obtained from the time-independent Schrodinger equation. One next considers “independence” and time reversal for each reaction. For example, consider two levels $n=1$ and $n=3$. An electron (as an example) may absorb a photon and move to level 3 or a photon may be emitted from level 3 and the electron drop to level 1. This is only one type of reaction, but if there is independence and time reversal, like in classical statistical mechanics, then one may consider an equation of the type.

$$P(n=1) \text{ Reaction}(1-3) = P(n=3) \text{ Reaction}(3-1) \quad ((10))$$

Taking natural logarithms of ((10)) leads to a conservation type equation. There is also the trivial conservation of energy relationship:

$$e_3 - e_1 = \text{energy difference} \quad ((11))$$

If one identifies $\ln(P(n=1))$ with $C - e_1/T$ one is led to a Maxwell-Boltzmann relationship $P(n=1) = C \exp(-e_1/T)$. ((12))

Ground State Quantum Oscillator

For the ground state quantum oscillator, $P(p) = \exp(-p^2/a)$ and $P(x) = \exp(-ax^2)$ where $a=E$ and $5kx^2 = 2a x^2$. Thus, for this case at this level of probabilities (i.e. not at the level of conditional probabilities), the oscillator matches classical statistical mechanics exactly. This seems to imply that:

$$P(p_1) V(\text{scattering } p_1 \text{ to } p_2) = P(p_2) V(\text{scattering } p_2 \text{ to } p_1) \quad ((13))$$

There are many p_i to p_j reactions, thus it seems each is independent and there is a time reversal balance. One may take the natural log of ((13)) and compare it to an energy

conservation type of equation containing $p_1^2/2m$ and $p_2^2/2m$. Then, comparing the two leads to:

$$P(p) = C \exp(-p^2/C_1) \text{ or the Maxwell-Boltzmann result.}$$

This does not occur, however, for higher energy oscillator states or for other potentials, and this begs the question: Why?

Dual Velocities in Bound State Quantum Mechanics

Bound state quantum mechanics seems to operate at two levels. One is: $P(p) = f_p \cdot f_p$ and $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction and the other: conditional probabilities $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$. A conditional probability is used to calculate the classical kinetic energy i.e:

$$(1/2m) \sum_p p^2 P(p/x) = .5 m v(x) v(x) \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{Where } .5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E. \quad P(p/x) = f_p/W \exp(ipx)$$

In addition, there are two velocities in bound state quantum mechanics, $v(x)$ and $u(x) = (1/W) d/dx W$. " $u(x)$ " is related to changes in density i.e. $d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x)W(x) u(x)$.

For the case of the ground state oscillator, one has the condition:

$$C_1 v(x)v(x) + C_2 u(x)u(x) = E \quad ((15))$$

If one takes the gradient of ((15)), one obtains identical kinematic force equations for $v(x)$ and $u(x)$ because $m/2 v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$. In other words $C_2 u(x)u(x)$ is like a potential. Thus, $v(x)$ and $u(x)$ behave in the same manner, so though there are two velocities, they behave the same way. It is as if one has one velocity. We think this may be why one may use a statement like ((13)) for the ground state oscillator and obtain a Maxwell-Boltzmann relationship. It seems there is independence and time reversal for each p reaction.

In general, however, ((15)) does not hold and $v(x)$ and $u(x)$ have different kinematical equations. $v(x)$ follows the usual Newton's law, as it is classical velocity, although obtained from conditional probabilities. Thus, the idea of equating:

$P(p_1) V(p_1 \text{ to } p_2)$ and $P(p_2) V(p_2 \text{ to } p_1)$ seems to break down. This seems to imply reactions are no longer independent as one has to maintain the behaviour of two velocities simultaneously. This is a different kind of statistical situation from Maxwell-Boltzmann ideas even though one has a time-independent equilibrium.

Thus, we argue that in cases, other than the ground state oscillator, bound state quantum mechanics is quite different from usual statistical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann type distribution $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ for momentum (although variations are possible), which appears both in classical and quantum mechanics, follows from “and” probability statements involving $P(p)$ or $P(e)$ (single particle energy= e) and utilises “independence of various reactions” and time reversal balance. Taking the natural logarithm yields a reaction conservation type equation which may be compared with an energy type conservation equation involving $p^2/2m$ or e . For a quantum oscillator ground state, this also holds, but not for other bound state cases and other potentials. We argue that in quantum mechanics there are two velocities $v(x)$, classical velocity, and $u(x)=1/W d/dx W$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. For the ground state oscillator $C_1 u(x)^2 + C_2 v(x)^2 = E$ so taking the gradient shows that $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ follow the same kinematics. Thus, it is as if there were one velocity and “independence and time reversal” seem to follow, leading to a Maxwell-Boltzmann type equation. For other cases, $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ follow very different kinematics, and the quantum distribution $W(x)$ or its Fourier transform f_p , must account for both simultaneously. This seems to lead to a breakdown in the picture of the “independence” of reactions and time reversal balance, even though energy type conservation equation still exist. It seems that it is the $\ln(P(p))$ type of reaction conservation equation that no longer holds. Thus, quantum mechanics appears to be a more complicated type of statistical equilibrium.

References

1. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley: New York, 1987)